

Project Number: 101030375

Project Acronym: TKTKGEN

Project title: TikTok and Generation Z: Online Participation and Identification in China and Italy

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN version 1 30/06/2022

1. Data Summary

This document describes the data management plan. It explains the purpose of data collection and generation, its relation to the objectives of the project, the way in which research data will be stored in relevant repositories and made available.

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Data will be collected for the purpose of sociological research on social media and youth culture in Italy and China, to explore the new practices of identification and belonging that are emerging within communities on video-sharing platforms such as TikTok.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Data gathered by the project will come in the form of audio, text and spreadsheets. Audio will be used to record interviews. They will be stored either in .wav or .mp3 formats. They will then be transcribed and stored as .rtf files. Spreadsheets will be used to store short responses from survey questions (in .csv format)

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

What is the origin of the data?

The origin of data will be research subjects participating in interviews and surveys

What is the expected size of the data?

I expect the total amount of data produced to be around 200GB (comprising heavy audio files)

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Mostly to other researchers working on similar issues (sociology of youth etc.)

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

The project will use the infrastructure and metadata naming procedures of Scuola Normale Superiore

What naming conventions do you follow?

I will use the acronym and the full name of project in all the relevant data documents

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Search keywords will be made available to optimize reuse

Do you provide clear version numbers?

The project will use version numbers

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

The data that will be publicly accessible will be the results of the survey. They will be available as spreadsheet files (csv)

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

The data will be made accessible through the public repository at Scuola Normale Superiore

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data can be download through an online web browser. Accessing data files can be done through proprietary software or through open-source software such as the spreadsheet application of LibreOffice packafge

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

NA, as it will not require particular software to access

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

NA

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

The data and associated metadata will be accessible on the official repository of Scuola Normale Superiore

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Yes, I have discussed arrangements with personnel responsible for data management at Scuola Normale Superiore

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

There are no restrictions on access

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Data will be made available in compliant formats (.csv) which is interoperable and can be used through different software packages both proprietary and open source

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

NA

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

NA

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

NA

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Data produced by the project will be available through a Creative Commons licence (CC BY)

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The data will be available as soon as it is ready, there will be no specific dates of release as release will depend on the development of the project. But all the relevant data will be made available for re-use before the end date of the project (31 December 2023). Data will not be embargoed

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

The data produced by the project (survey data) is reusable and there is not date to its use.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will remain permanently reusable

Are data quality assurance processes described?

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

There are no costs involved in abiding with data FAIR requirements.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

NA

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Myself as the Project Coordinator

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

NA

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

The data will be backed up on a monthly basis and securely stored on the repository fo Scuola Normale Superiore

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The data will be stored in the certified repository of Scuola Normale Superiore

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

The project raises some ethical issues that have been covered in the research ethics deliverables. However only the data from the surveys will be made available. This is anonymised at the source and therefore it will not raise particular ethical questions.

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

NA

2.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so • Specify how the data will be made available • Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? • Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited • Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions
2.3. Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. • Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible • Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed • Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why • Describe data quality assurance processes • Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable
3. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs • Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project • Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
4. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
5. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
6. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	13.10.2016	▪ Initial version